

Determinants of Purchase Decision: The Role of Product Quality, Brand Image, and Price

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of product quality, brand image, and price on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets. This study employed a quantitative explanatory research design. The population consisted of consumers who had purchased Wilson tennis rackets through the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas. Using purposive sampling, 100 respondents were selected as the research sample. Data analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression with SPSS, including instrument testing, classical assumption testing, hypothesis testing, and coefficient of determination analysis. The findings indicate that product quality, brand image, and price each have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Brand image was identified as the most dominant factor influencing purchase decisions. The coefficient of determination test showed that 94.0% of the variance in purchase decisions could be explained by the three independent variables included in the model. These findings reinforce Consumer Behavior Theory by confirming that purchasing decisions for premium sports products are shaped by both functional product evaluations and psychological brand perceptions. Practically, sellers and distributors of Wilson tennis rackets should prioritize strengthening brand image, maintaining product quality, and implementing value-based pricing strategies to improve consumer purchase decisions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the global sports industry has shown a significant increase in demand for premium sports equipment, including tennis rackets, in line with growing public participation in tennis as part of a healthy lifestyle and recreational activity. International tennis federations have reported growth in the number of active tennis players worldwide in recent years, directly contributing to the expansion of the global tennis equipment market (Bowers, 2024). Specifically, the global tennis racket market is projected to exceed USD 684 million by 2030, with a stable annual growth rate (Grand View Research, 2024). This phenomenon indicates that competition among tennis racket manufacturers is becoming increasingly intense, requiring companies to better understand the factors influencing consumer purchasing decisions. In such a competitive market, consumers have become more selective in evaluating product quality, brand reputation, and price before making a purchase. Therefore, research on the determinants of tennis racket purchasing decisions is important to provide empirical insight into consumer behavior in the premium sports equipment market.

The relevant theoretical foundation for this study is Consumer Behavior Theory, which explains that purchasing decisions result from consumers' evaluation of product attributes based on perceived benefits, value, and expected satisfaction (Kotler & Keller, 2016). This theory emphasizes that consumers consider various marketing stimuli before purchasing, including product quality as a representation of performance and durability, brand image as a psychological association with product reputation, and

price as an indicator of economic value and fairness of consumer sacrifice (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2015). In the context of this study, Consumer Behavior Theory explains that the purchase decision for Wilson tennis rackets occurs through consumers' evaluation of perceived racket quality, the strength of Wilson's brand image in the global market, and the suitability of price relative to the benefits received.

The selection of Wilson tennis rackets as the research object is based on Wilson's position as one of the global market leaders in the premium tennis racket industry. Wilson is used by approximately 26–31% of Top 100 ATP Tour players and more than 40% of top WTA players, indicating strong brand reputation and credibility in the professional tennis market (Barker, 2023; Crim, 2024). In addition, Wilson, together with Head, controls approximately 20–25% of the global tennis racket market share (Ken Research, 2024). In Indonesia, Wilson rackets are also among the most widely sold tennis racket products through marketplaces and social media, including the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas, which consistently sells Wilson products with high sales volume. This condition shows that Wilson is a relevant and representative object for examining consumer purchasing decision behavior regarding premium sports products marketed digitally.

Although numerous studies have examined the effects of product quality, brand image, and price on purchasing decisions, research gaps remain due to inconsistent empirical findings (Muhammad, Edy & Tia, Chisca, 2023). (Marbun et al., 2022) found that brand image had no significant effect on purchasing decisions, while product quality and price were significant. In contrast, Dewi et al. found that product quality had no significant effect on Yonex racket purchases, whereas brand image was the dominant variable. Likewise, (Lupiyoadi & Hamdani, 2020) reported that brand image did not significantly influence purchasing decisions, although product quality and price had positive effects. These inconsistencies indicate that the relationships among product quality, brand image, price, and purchasing decisions remain contextual and may vary depending on product characteristics, industry category, and purchasing channel. Moreover, most prior studies focused on sports fashion products and offline purchases, while research on premium sports equipment remains limited.

Based on this gap, the present study aims to provide empirical contribution by re-examining the effects of product quality, brand image, and price on purchasing decisions in the context of premium tennis racket products sold through digital social marketplaces, specifically Wilson tennis rackets purchased by consumers of the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas. Empirically, this study expands evidence regarding the determinants of purchasing decisions in the premium sports equipment industry. Theoretically, it strengthens the application of Consumer Behavior Theory in the context of premium sports product purchases through social media. Practically, the findings are expected to serve as a basis for Wilson and independent sellers such as @rakettenisbekas in formulating more effective marketing strategies through improvements in product quality, strengthening brand image, and setting prices aligned with consumers' value perceptions. The novelty of this study lies in testing a purchasing decision model for premium tennis racket products using Wilson as the object within the context of digital sales through Instagram, which remains underexplored in previous studies. Accordingly, the objective of this study is to analyze and empirically test the effects of product quality, brand image, and price on purchasing decisions for Wilson tennis rackets, both partially and simultaneously.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Behavior Theory

Consumer Behavior Theory proposed by (Kotler & Keller, 2016) explains that consumer behavior is the process by which individuals or groups select, purchase, use, and evaluate products or services to satisfy their needs and wants. According to this theory, purchase decisions are influenced by various marketing stimuli, including product attributes, brand perceptions, and price considerations. Consumers evaluate the benefits and value offered by a product before making a purchase decision. This theory is relevant to the present study because it explains that consumers' purchase decisions regarding Wilson tennis rackets result from their evaluation of product quality, brand image, and price during the decision-making process.

Product Quality

Product quality refers to a product's ability to perform its functions, including durability, reliability, precision, ease of use, and other attributes that provide value to consumers (Fachrozi et al., 2023). In this study, product quality refers to consumers' perceptions of the performance, materials, durability, features, and comfort of Wilson tennis rackets in supporting tennis activities. The higher the perceived product quality, the greater the likelihood of consumers making a purchase decision.

Brand Image

Brand image is the set of perceptions, beliefs, and impressions held in consumers' minds regarding a brand based on their experiences, information, and associations with that brand (Sari et al., 2024). Brand image reflects the reputation, credibility, and symbolic identity of a brand in consumers' perceptions. In this study, Wilson's brand image represents consumers' perceptions of Wilson as a global tennis racket brand that is high-quality, professional, and prestigious. A strong brand image can increase consumer trust and encourage purchase decisions.

Price

Price is the amount of money consumers must pay to obtain the benefits of a product or service (Kotler et al., 2022). Price is

one of the main considerations in evaluating product value because it reflects the sacrifice consumers make relative to the benefits received. In this study, price refers to consumers' perceptions of the affordability, fairness, and appropriateness of Wilson tennis racket prices relative to their quality and benefits.

Purchase Decision

Purchase decision is the stage in the consumer decision-making process when an individual decides to buy a particular product after evaluating available alternatives (Kotler et al., 2022). In this study, purchase decision refers to consumers' actions in selecting, purchasing, and deciding to use Wilson tennis rackets based on their evaluation of product quality, brand image, and price.

Hypothesis Development

The Effect of Product Quality on Purchase Decision

According to Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by their evaluation of product attributes perceived as capable of fulfilling needs and providing superior value compared to alternatives. One of the primary attributes considered in this evaluation process is product quality. Product quality reflects a product's ability to perform its core functions, including durability, reliability, performance, features, and conformity with consumer expectations. In the context of purchasing Wilson tennis rackets, consumers tend to evaluate product quality based on playing performance, racket materials, applied technology, comfort of use, and product durability before making a purchase decision. The higher consumers perceive the quality of Wilson tennis rackets, the greater the likelihood of purchase decisions, as high-quality products are considered capable of delivering optimal benefits and reducing purchase risk. This finding is supported by previous studies (Jung et al., 2021; Wibowo & Sutanto, 2023; Windarti & Ibrahim, 2017), which demonstrate that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Product quality has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets.

The Effect of Brand Image on Purchase Decision

According to Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by perceptions, beliefs, and associations formed in consumers' minds regarding a brand. Brand image represents the overall consumer perception of a brand, reflected through its reputation, credibility, prestige, and associated experiences. In the purchasing decision-making process, consumers tend to choose products with strong brand images because such brands are perceived to provide quality assurance, reduce perceived risk, and increase trust in the purchased product. In the context of purchasing Wilson tennis rackets, Wilson's brand image as a global brand used by many professional athletes and possessing a strong reputation in the tennis equipment industry may become an important factor influencing consumer purchase decisions. The more positive Wilson's brand image in consumers' minds, the greater the likelihood that consumers will choose and purchase the product. This statement is supported by previous studies (Erida et al., 2020; Rizq & Muslichah, 2023; Windyaswara & Cokki, 2024), which found that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Brand image has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets.

The Effect of Price on Purchase Decision

According to Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), price is one of the marketing stimuli that becomes a major consideration for consumers in evaluating product value before making a purchase decision. Consumers generally compare the financial sacrifice required with the benefits or quality expected from the product. A price perceived as fair, competitive, and aligned with product quality will enhance consumers' perceived value, thereby encouraging purchase decisions. In the context of purchasing Wilson tennis rackets, consumers will assess whether the offered price is proportional to the material quality, technology, performance, and brand reputation associated with the product. If the price of Wilson rackets is considered appropriate relative to the benefits and quality received, consumers will be more likely to make a purchase. Conversely, if the price is perceived as too high relative to the perceived value, purchase decisions may decline. This finding is supported by previous studies (Marbun et al., 2022; Saifuddin, 2019; Setiowaty & Winarningsih, 2017), which prove that price has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Price has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets.

III. METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design, aiming to explain the causal relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable, namely the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets. The quantitative approach is chosen because the study focuses on hypothesis testing through numerical measurement and statistical analysis to determine the magnitude of relationships between variables empirically (Ghozali, 2021).

The population in this study consists of all consumers who have purchased Wilson tennis rackets through the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas in Indonesia. Since the exact population size is unknown (infinite population), the sampling technique used is non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, where respondents are selected based on specific criteria relevant to the research objectives. The criteria include: (1) having purchased a Wilson tennis racket through the Instagram account

@rakettenisbekas within the last year, (2) being at least 18 years old, and (3) being willing to complete the questionnaire in full.

The sample size determination refers to (Ferdinand, 2016; Ghozali, 2021) who state that the minimum sample size in multivariate research is 5–10 times the number of indicators. This study includes 20 measurement indicators, resulting in a minimum sample size of 100 respondents. Therefore, this study uses 100 respondents, which is considered sufficient to meet the requirements for multiple linear regression analysis.

Indikator penelitian dalam studi ini disusun berdasarkan konsep teoritis dari masing-masing variabel yang The research indicators are developed based on the theoretical concepts of each variable, namely product quality, brand image, price, and purchase decision. Product quality is measured through indicators such as product performance, durability, reliability, and comfort of use, reflecting the ability of Wilson tennis rackets to meet consumer needs during tennis activities (Iqbal & Suzianti, 2021; Paparella et al., 2020). Brand image is measured through indicators including brand reputation, brand recognition, brand trust, and positive consumer associations with Wilson as a global tennis racket brand (Liang et al., 2024; Sari et al., 2024). Price is measured using indicators such as price affordability, price–quality conformity, price competitiveness, and price–benefit suitability perceived by consumers (Liu et al., 2022; Novrianda, 2018). Meanwhile, purchase decision is measured through indicators including purchase confidence, product preference, decision firmness, and willingness to repurchase or recommend the product to others (Elshaer et al., 2024; Marbun et al., 2022; Solomon, 2018).

Data collection was conducted using an online questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software through several stages. First, instrument testing was conducted, consisting of validity and reliability tests. Second, classical assumption tests were performed, including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests to ensure the feasibility of the regression model. Third, multiple linear regression analysis was used to examine the effect of product quality, brand image, and price on purchase decision. Hypothesis testing was then conducted using the t-test to examine the partial effects of each independent variable, and the coefficient of determination (R^2) to determine the extent to which the independent variables explain the variation in purchase decisions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

Based on the respondent characteristics, the majority of Wilson tennis racket consumers from the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas are male (63%), indicating that the primary market segment in this study is still dominated by male consumers. In terms of age, most respondents fall within the 21–30 years group (52%), suggesting that the main consumers are young adults who are actively productive and have a strong interest in tennis.

Regarding domicile, most respondents are from Java Island (60%), indicating that the primary market is concentrated in regions with higher sports activity levels and better market access. Based on occupation, the majority of respondents are students (40%), indicating that the Wilson tennis racket market is relatively strong among higher education groups and young sports communities.

Furthermore, most respondents have used Wilson rackets for 7–12 months (45%), indicating sufficient experience to objectively evaluate product quality. In terms of playing frequency, the majority play tennis 1–2 times per week (44%), meaning most respondents are active users rather than passive buyers. Therefore, their perceptions of product quality, brand image, price, and purchase decisions are considered relevant and reliable for this study.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	63	63%
	Female	37	37%
Age	<20 years	7	7%
	21–30 years	52	52%
	31–40 years	33	33%
	>40 years	8	8%
Domicile	Java	60	60%
	Sumatra	18	18%
	Bali / Nusa Tenggara	10	10%
	Kalimantan	8	8%
	Papua	4	4%
Occupation	Student	40	40%
	Private Employee	25	25%
	Government Employee	10	10%
	Entrepreneur	15	15%
	Others	10	10%

Duration of Wilson Racket Use	<3 months	18	18%
	3–6 months	37	37%
	7–12 months	45	45%
Tennis Playing Frequency	1x/week	21	21%
	1–2x/week	44	44%
	>3x/week	35	35%
Total			100%

Source: Own data research, 2026

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Product Quality (X1)	100	4	20	17.98	2.41
Brand Image (X2)	100	4	20	18.39	2.16
Price (X3)	100	4	20	17.72	2.35
Purchase Decision (Y)	100	4	20	17.68	2.57

Source: Own data research, 2026

Based on the descriptive statistical results, the brand image variable has the highest mean value of 18.39, indicating that Wilson’s brand image is the most strongly perceived aspect by respondents. Meanwhile, the price variable has the lowest mean value of 17.72, although it still falls within a high category. Overall, all research variables show mean scores close to the maximum value, indicating that respondents provide positive evaluations of product quality, brand image, price, and purchase decisions of Wilson tennis rackets.

Table 3. Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	r-count	r-table	Description
(X1) Product Quality	X1.1	0.921	0.196	Valid
	X1.2	0.905	0.196	Valid
	X1.3	0.898	0.196	Valid
	X1.4	0.902	0.196	Valid
(X2) Brand Image	X2.1	0.898	0.196	Valid
	X2.2	0.888	0.196	Valid
	X2.3	0.907	0.196	Valid
	X2.4	0.876	0.196	Valid
(X3) Price	X3.1	0.898	0.196	Valid
	X3.2	0.929	0.196	Valid
	X3.3	0.903	0.196	Valid
	X3.4	0.900	0.196	Valid
(Y) Purchase Decision	Y1.1	0.896	0.196	Valid
	Y1.2	0.919	0.196	Valid
	Y1.3	0.914	0.196	Valid
	Y1.4	0.884	0.196	Valid

Source: Own data research, 2026

Based on the validity test results, all indicators of product quality, brand image, price, and purchase decision variables have r-count values greater than the r-table value of 0.196. The r-count values range from 0.876 to 0.929, indicating that all questionnaire items are valid. This shows that each indicator accurately measures its respective construct and is appropriate for use as a research instrument in studying the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets.

Table 4. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Description
(X1) Product Quality	0.928	Reliable
(X2) Brand Image	0.914	Reliable
(X3) Price	0.928	Reliable
(Y) Purchase Decision	0.924	Reliable

Source: Own data research, 2026

Based on the reliability test results, all research variables have Cronbach’s Alpha values above 0.60, ranging from 0.914 to 0.928. Therefore, product quality, brand image, price, and purchase decision variables are considered reliable. This indicates that all instruments have very high internal consistency and are suitable for use in further statistical analysis.

Table 5. Classical Assumption Tests

Variable	Glejser test (Sig.)	VIF	Normality Test Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Product Quality	0.592	8.301	0,200
Brand Image	0.866	9.512	
Price	0.817	8.699	

Source: Own data research, 2026

Based on the classical assumption test results, the regression model in this study meets all required assumptions. The normality test shows an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that the residuals are normally distributed. The Glejser test results show that all independent variables have significance values above 0.05 (product quality = 0.592, brand image = 0.866, price = 0.817), indicating no heteroscedasticity. Furthermore, the multicollinearity test shows that all VIF values are below 10 (product quality = 8.301, brand image = 9.512, price = 8.699), indicating no multicollinearity among independent variables. Thus, the regression model is considered appropriate for hypothesis testing.

Table 6. Hypothesis Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.678	0.326		2.077	0.041
	Product Quality	0.354	0.070	0.361	5.079	0.000
	Brand Image	0.399	0.075	0.404	5.303	0.000
	Price	0.222	0.070	0.230	3.161	0.002
2	Coefficient of Determination	R=0.970	R ² =0.941	Adjusted R ² =0.940		

Source: Own data research, 2026

Based on the hypothesis testing results, all independent variables have a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets. Product quality has a regression coefficient of 0.354 with a t-value of 5.079 and a significance value of 0.000, indicating a positive and significant effect. Brand image has a coefficient of 0.399 with a t-value of 5.303 and a significance value of 0.000, also indicating a positive and significant effect. Price has a coefficient of 0.222 with a t-value of 3.161 and a significance value of 0.002, indicating a positive and significant influence. Therefore, all hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3) are accepted.

Based on the standardized beta values, the most dominant variable influencing purchase decision is brand image ($\beta = 0.404$), followed by product quality ($\beta = 0.361$), and price ($\beta = 0.230$). This indicates that brand image is the strongest factor affecting consumer purchase decisions.

Meanwhile, the coefficient of determination shows an R² value of 0.941 and an Adjusted R² of 0.940, meaning that 94.0% of the variation in purchase decision can be explained by product quality, brand image, and price. The remaining 6.0% is explained by other factors outside the model that were not examined in this study.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Product Quality on the Purchase Decision

The hypothesis testing results show that product quality has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets, as indicated by a regression coefficient of 0.354, a t-value of 5.079, and a significance level of 0.000. This finding indicates that the higher consumers’ perception of Wilson’s product quality, the stronger their tendency to make a purchase decision. From the perspective of Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), product quality is a key attribute evaluated by consumers during the decision-making process because it reflects the product’s ability to deliver benefits, performance, and satisfaction in line with expectations. The theory emphasizes that consumers tend to choose products perceived as high quality because they reduce purchase risk and increase perceived utility. Therefore, this study reinforces the argument that product quality is a critical determinant of purchase decisions, especially for premium sports products that require high technical performance such as tennis rackets.

In the context of this study, the positive effect of product quality indicates that consumers consider performance, durability, material, racket technology, and comfort of use as the main factors before purchasing Wilson tennis rackets. This is reasonable since a tennis racket is not merely a general consumer product but a sports equipment that directly affects playing performance. Consumers are more likely to purchase Wilson rackets when they believe the product offers better control, power, durability, and comfort

compared to alternative brands. Thus, perceived product quality becomes the rational basis for evaluating whether Wilson rackets are worth purchasing according to their playing needs. This finding is consistent with (Jung et al., 2021), who found that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, where consumers tend to choose high-quality products because they provide greater benefits. It also supports (Wibowo & Sutanto, 2023; Windarti & Ibrahim, 2017), who confirmed that product quality is a dominant factor influencing consumer purchase decisions.

Practically, these findings imply that Wilson racket sellers and distributors should consistently emphasize product quality in their marketing strategy. In the context of sales through the Instagram account @rakettenisbekas, detailed communication regarding technical specifications, product condition, authenticity, frame technology, and performance benefits should be highlighted. This is important because premium sports consumers tend to conduct in-depth evaluations before purchasing. Strengthening perceived product quality will increase the likelihood of purchase decisions.

Effect of Brand Image on the Purchase Decision

The hypothesis testing results indicate that brand image has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets, with a regression coefficient of 0.399, a t-value of 5.303, and a significance level of 0.000. This shows that a more positive brand image leads to a higher likelihood of purchase decisions. According to Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), purchase decisions are not only influenced by rational evaluation of product attributes but also by psychological perceptions and associations attached to a brand. Brand image serves as a symbolic representation that helps consumers assess reputation, quality, and credibility when facing multiple alternatives. Therefore, consumers tend to choose brands with a strong image because they are perceived as more trustworthy and capable of delivering higher functional and emotional value.

In this study, the positive effect of brand image indicates that consumers strongly consider Wilson's global reputation as a well-established tennis equipment brand. Wilson's status as a brand widely used by professional athletes and its long-standing reputation for producing high-quality rackets create a strong positive perception among consumers. This perception strengthens the belief that purchasing Wilson rackets is the right decision in terms of both performance and prestige. Thus, in premium sports products, brand image functions not only as product identity but also as a quality signal and status symbol. This result aligns with (Erida et al., 2020), who found that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, as well as (Rizq & Muslichah, 2023; Windyaswara & Cokki, 2024), who emphasized that strong brand image increases consumer trust and loyalty.

Practically, sellers and distributors should continuously strengthen Wilson's brand image through digital marketing strategies, especially on Instagram @rakettenisbekas. Efforts may include highlighting global reputation, endorsements by professional athletes, customer testimonials, product authenticity, and premium brand positioning. Since brand image is the most dominant factor influencing purchase decisions, strengthening it consistently will significantly increase consumer trust and purchase likelihood.

Effect of Price on the Purchase Decision

The hypothesis testing results show that price has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets, with a regression coefficient of 0.222, a t-value of 3.161, and a significance level of 0.002. This indicates that the more appropriate consumers perceive the price of Wilson rackets, the higher their likelihood of purchasing. According to Consumer Behavior Theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016), price is a primary marketing stimulus used by consumers to evaluate product value before making a purchase decision. Consumers compare the financial sacrifice required with the expected benefits, quality, and satisfaction. When price is perceived as proportional to the benefits received, perceived value increases and encourages purchase decisions.

In this context, consumers consider the alignment between price and product quality, performance, and brand reputation. Although Wilson rackets are positioned as premium products with relatively higher prices, consumers are still willing to purchase them when they perceive that the price reflects superior materials, technology, durability, and brand prestige. This shows that in premium sports markets, price is not only seen as a cost but also as a representation of value and quality. This finding is consistent with (Marbun et al., 2022; Saifuddin, 2019; Setiowaty & Winarningsih, 2017), who found that price has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. However, its influence is weaker compared to product quality and brand image, indicating that consumers are more value-oriented than price-sensitive.

Practically, sellers should apply a value-based pricing strategy, especially on Instagram @rakettenisbekas. The price should be clearly communicated as being proportional to quality, condition, technology, and brand prestige. Transparency, detailed product information, and varied price options can help improve perceived price fairness and strengthen purchase decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

The main findings of this study indicate that product quality, brand image, and price have a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Wilson tennis rackets. Among these variables, brand image has the most dominant influence, followed by product quality and price. This confirms that consumer purchase decisions are not only based on functional product evaluation but are also strongly influenced by perceptions of brand reputation and prestige.

These results show that purchase decisions for premium sports products are formed through a combination of rational evaluation of product attributes and psychological evaluation of brand perception. Therefore, the success of Wilson racket marketing depends not only on objective product quality but also on strong brand image development and value-based pricing strategies.

Theoretically, this study supports Consumer Behavior Theory, which states that purchase decisions are influenced by product attributes, brand perception, and price considerations as key marketing stimuli. Practically, it provides guidance for Wilson racket sellers to prioritize brand strengthening, maintain product quality, and apply value-based pricing strategies.

This study has limitations. It focuses only on consumers purchasing through a single Instagram account, uses only three independent variables, and applies a cross-sectional design. Future research is recommended to expand the scope of brands and platforms, include additional variables such as electronic word of mouth, brand loyalty, or consumer trust, and use more advanced methods such as SEM or longitudinal analysis to better capture consumer behavior dynamics in premium sports equipment markets.

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VII. DISCLOSURE

The author reports no conflicts of interest in this work.

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